

Blizzard Challenge 2027: Accented Zero-Shot TTS in Spontaneous Portuguese Speech (Training Material)

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Resumo This report details the training material for the Blizzard Challenge 2027, which focuses on accented zero-shot Text-to-Speech (TTS) in spontaneous Portuguese. We describe three primary datasets: NURC-SP (São Paulo), NURC-RE (Recife), and FalAR-TTS (European Portuguese).

1 Introduction

Developing Text-to-Speech (TTS) systems for spontaneous speech requires high-fidelity data capable of capturing natural prosodic phenomena that may be absent in read speech, such as segmental reductions, fillers, and self-corrections.

A primary challenge in synthesizing Portuguese is the vast geographical distribution of its speakers; Brazil’s continental dimensions foster immense internal diversity with distinct regional accents, while the great distance from Portugal further accentuates the phonetic and prosodic divergences between Brazilian and European varieties.

Historically, Portuguese speech resources were largely restricted to read, planned speech, leaving regional varieties and spontaneous styles under-represented. To address this, the Blizzard Challenge 2027 leverages the emergence of large-scale digitized corpora. For Brazilian Portuguese, the Cultured Urban Linguistic Norm Project (NURC) (*Norma Urbana Linguística Culta*), conceived in 1969 with the objective of studying the cultured urban norm spoken in five Brazilian capitals — Recife, Salvador, Rio de Janeiro, São Paulo and Porto Alegre, compiled a large corpus for each capital, about three hundred hours, with varying recording quality, including research in three different textual genres. The informers have an academic degree, are born in the city under study, and are children of native Portuguese speakers. There is a balance between the masculine and feminine genders and three age ranges of informants: 25 to 35 years, 36 to 55 years

and over 56 years. For the Blizzard Challenge 2027 we will focus on the data from São Paulo (NURC-SP) and Recife (NURC-RE).

These resources are complemented by the FalAR-TTS corpus, a subset of the larger FalAR dataset [6], a massive collection of speaker- and age-annotated parliamentary speeches, to bridge the data gap for European Portuguese.

2 Datasets

The following subsections provide a comprehensive description of the three corpora selected for the Challenge: NURC-TTS (grouping NURC-SP and NURC-RE), and FalAR-TTS. These resources were specifically curated to represent the phonetic and prosodic diversity of the Portuguese language in different regions and speech styles, ranging from formal parliamentary interventions to highly spontaneous dialogues.

2.1 NURC-TTS

Links:

https://huggingface.co/datasets/nilc-nlp/nurc_tts

https://huggingface.co/datasets/nilc-nlp/nurc_tts_24khz

splits: sao_paulo and recife

NURC-SP (São Paulo Accent): The São Paulo collection specifically documents the speech of individuals born in the capital of São Paulo state, with high formal education. It is the first large-scale spontaneous speech corpus dedicated to the Paulistano accent.

The dataset is predominantly composed of interviews (DID) and dialogues (D2), which account for 90% of the material. Linguistic features include a high frequency of orality marks, filled pauses (e.g., “eh”, “ah”, “mm”), and editing disfluencies like word repetitions and revisions. A notable dialectal trait in São Paulo included in the corpus is the elision of final post-tonic vowels (/a/, /o/, /u/) in word boundaries.

The NURC-SP Audio Corpus [3] consists of 239.30 hours of speech from 401 speakers. Originally recorded on analog reel-to-reel tapes, the material was digitized by CEDAE/UNICAMP⁶. Automatic transcriptions were initially generated using WhisperX⁷ (Large-v2 model) with pyannote-audio for diarization. These were then manually revised by 14 native speakers between June and December 2023. Filtering removed segments with high background noise, overlapping voices, or severe distortion.

⁶ <https://www.iel.unicamp.br/cedae/>

⁷ <https://github.com/m-bain/whisperX>

NURC-RE (Recife Accent): The NURC-RE corpus documents the cultured urban norm of Recife, Pernambuco. It serves as a foundational resource for Brazilian sociolinguistics, specifically capturing the unique phonetic and prosodic features of the Northeast region.

The digitized collection for Recife is extensive, comprising a total of 316 inquiries. The distribution of these inquiries according to the project’s traditional textual genres is as follows:

- **DID** (Dialogue between Informant and Documenter): 238 inquiries, totaling approximately 191 hours of recorded speech;
- **D2** (Dialogue between two informants): 41 inquiries, providing roughly 75 hours of spontaneous interaction;
- **EF** (Formal Elocution): 37 inquiries, representing about 24 hours of formal lectures and elocutions.

While the full corpus provides a broad dialectal overview, a specialized “Shared Corpus” subset consisting of 32 inquiries (12 EF, 12 DID, and 8 D2) is available for high-precision tasks. These specific recordings are accompanied by multi-level annotation files and aligned prosodic information in TextGrid (Praat) and .eaf (ELAN) formats, facilitating detailed speech synthesis research. All this dataset is part of the NURC Digital Project⁸.

The NURC Digital Project aimed to develop specific methodologies and practices for managing sound recordings resulting from the NURC Project, as well as strategies for migrating to digital formats, curating, and digitally preserving this collection. The paper [4] provides more information about the NURC Digital Project and should be used as a reference for the data provided here.

Curation for Blizzard: For the challenge, we chose to re-segment both datasets for two main reasons: a) the NURC-SP segments had a 16kHz sampling rate as they were created by WhisperX, which may be considered insufficient for the TTS task, whereas the original audios are at 44.1kHz; b) there were many short segments of 1 and 2 seconds; in cases where these segments were sequential, we concatenated them.

The executed pipeline was:

1. Downloading the original inquiry audios;
2. Reading the segments and transcriptions (from CSV in the case of SP and TextGrid in the case of RE);
3. Re-segmentation via a Python *librosa* script, concatenating sequential segments shorter than 3 seconds;
4. The transcription was normalized to lowercase;
5. Segments shorter than 3 seconds and longer than 30 seconds were removed.

The final result consists of 321k segments and 472 hours, with 121k (231h) from São Paulo and 200k (241h) from Recife; the Recife segmentation contains

⁸ <https://fale.ufal.br/projeto/nurcdigital/>

shorter clips, see Figure 1. The main repository has a 44.1kHz sampling rate, while the `nurc_tts_24khz` is at 24kHz. It is important to note that the original recordings were made from analog reel-to-reel tapes; therefore, the final audio quality does not strictly correspond to these values.

Figure 1: NURC-TTS Segments distribution by duration

The HuggingFace Dataset fields are explained at Table 1.

Tabela 1: Dataset Fields and Descriptions

Field	Description
<code>inquiry</code>	The ID of the original recording session (e.g., <code>SP_D2_015</code>).
<code>segment</code>	Path or identifier for the specific audio segment.
<code>speaker</code>	Integer ID assigned to the speaker (Note: WhisperX-generated IDs may have minor inaccuracies).
<code>duration</code>	Total length of the audio segment in seconds.
<code>text</code>	Human-made transcription including prosodic and orality markings.
<code>normalized_text</code>	Human-made transcription cleaned of prosodic markings for standard training.
<code>inq_type</code>	Genre classification: EF (Formal Elocution), DID (Inquiry/Interview), or D2 (Dialogue).
<code>inq_recording_year</code>	The year the session was recorded.
<code>inq_gender</code>	Speaker’s gender (F, M, or combinations like F e M for multi-speaker inquiries).
<code>inq_age_group</code>	Age category: I (25-35), II (36-55), or III (55+).
<code>inq_quality</code>	Human-determined audio quality (e.g., Excellent, Good, Regular).
<code>inq_themes</code>	Topic of the speech (e.g., “Vegetais, agricultura”).
<code>audio</code>	The actual audio data for the segment.

2.2 FalAR-TTS (European Portuguese)

FalAR [6] is a large-scale European Portuguese corpus comprising 5,800 hours of spoken utterances recorded, mostly, in the plenary sessions of the Portuguese Parliament. Within this dataset, 4,850 hours are annotated with speaker identities across 1,180 distinct individuals, alongside comprehensive metadata including age, gender, political affiliation, and parliamentary role. The corpus was primarily designed to train and benchmark Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) and speaker diarization systems, featuring aligned audio and orthographic transcripts from parliamentary sessions. Because the dataset spans recordings from 2006 onward, various recording setups were adopted over time, introducing some longitudinal variations in the acoustic characteristics of the speech signals.

Data Selection To minimize variations in recording setups and acoustic environments, the FalAR-TTS⁹ corpus was constructed by extracting a restricted temporal subset of the broader FalAR data, specifically spanning the years 2016 and 2017. Furthermore, since the audio segmentation process relies on aligning official parliamentary reference transcripts with timestamped automatic transcriptions generated by CAMOES models [2], a rigorous data filtering criterion was applied. Only speech segments longer than five seconds that yielded a Character Error Rate (CER) below 15% during the reference-to-automatic alignment phase were selected for inclusion. Figure 2 illustrates the overall CER distribution across the corpus.

The resulting FalAR-TTS dataset comprises 280 speakers, consisting of 180 male speakers (accounting for 221 hours of audio) and 100 female speakers (97 hours). Figure 3 depicts the distribution of the recorded material across the corpus speakers, while Figure 4 displays the histogram of individual file durations. Finally, all audio files are delivered at a sampling rate of 24 kHz.

The HuggingFace Dataset fields are explained at Table 2.

⁹ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/inesc-id/FalAR-TTS>

Figura 2: FalAR-TTS Segments distribution by Character Error Rate

Tabela 2: Dataset Fields and Descriptions

Field	Description
file_name	The actual audio data for the segment.
speaker_id	Integer ID assigned to the speaker recorded in this file during the annotation process.
gender	Gender of the speaker recorded in this file.
age	The age of the speaker (in years) at the time of the recording.
ref_trans_clean	A clean orthographic transcript sourced from the Portuguese Parliament archive, which is natively devoid of repetitions, hesitations, and speech disfluencies.
asr_trans	Automatic content transcription produced by CAMOES ASR models.
cer	Character Error Rate computed from the alignment between the reference (ref_trans_clean) and the automatic transcripts (asr_trans).
raw_stm_content	A fine-grained, timestamped automatic transcript of the spoken content.

Segment Time Mark (STM) Annotations To expand the characterization of the dataset, each audio file — nominally containing speech from a single individual — was processed using the Pyannote [1] speaker diarization framework. The resulting outputs were utilized to isolate overlapping speech intervals and to extract speaker embeddings via SpeechBrain’s pre-trained ECAPA-TDNN model [5]. These embeddings allowed for the detection of file-wise acoustic outliers based on average pairwise cosine similarity calculations.

In addition to the raw audio, the dataset includes a "raw_stm_content" field, which enables the reconstruction of an STM file. This file contains timestamped

Figura 3: Distribution of speech material across FalAR-TTS speakers.

speech segments and their corresponding automatic transcriptions, augmented with two distinct metadata annotations appended in an [A|B] format:

- **A:** The average cosine similarity between the current speaker embedding and those computed for the remaining speaker turns within the file (evaluates to "n/a" if the speaker segmentation yields only a single speaker turn);
- **B:** The ratio of the overlapping speech span to the total segment duration.

Link:

<https://huggingface.co/datasets/inesc-id/FalAR-TTS>

2.3 More information

- Description of the Blizzard Challenge 2027 ::
<https://nilc-nlp.github.io/ssw-2027/blizzard-challenge-dates.html>
- Rules of the challenge ::
<https://nilc-nlp.github.io/ssw-2027/blizzard-challenge-rules.html>

3 Concluding Remarks

The Blizzard Challenge 2027 is intended to provide a unique opportunity to advance Text-to-Speech (TTS) research in the Portuguese language by focusing on regional diversity and the intricacies of spontaneous speech. It is expected that the provision of the NURC-SP, NURC-RE, and FalAR datasets will serve as a robust foundation for participants to explore the phonetic and prosodic nuances of the Lusophone world.

By utilizing these resources, which capture everything from formal parliamentary interventions in Portugal to spontaneous dialogues in São Paulo and

Figura 4: FalAR-TTS File distribution by duration

Recife, we hope the research community can move toward creating more inclusive and natural-sounding speech synthesis. Ultimately, these materials are expected to help bridge the gap between traditional read-speech models and the complex reality of spontaneous, accented communication.

Referências

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